

End-to-End Optimization of the Pulse Shaper for Enhanced Residual Phase Noise Resilience

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Abstract: We leverage an autoencoder to optimize the pulse shaper and matched filter under residual phase noise (RPN) influence. The learned filters effectively cancel the distortions caused by RPN, enhancing the robustness of the transmitted constellation.

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1. Introduction

The tracking of phase noise is one of the most vital digital signal processing (DSP) subsystems in coherent transmission, as it enables the information to be sent sturdily in classical quadrature and amplitude modulation (QAM) formats [1]. However, as we increase the modulation order of QAM systems, the tolerance to phase noise decreases, typically demanding more efforts to be put into carrier phase estimation (CPE): either a larger overhead for the finer tracking of phase fluctuations, in the case of pilot-aided CPE, or through more complex blind phase estimation algorithms, such as the blind phase search (BPS) algorithm. The less attention we put into the CPE subsystem, the more residual phase noise (RPN) will be left in the constellation, hindering the correct retrieval of the transmitted symbols.

One alternative to improving CPE subsystems is to build more RPN-resilient DSP blocks, allowing for a relaxation of the CPE requirements. While this problem was not particularly targeted in the past, the advent of machine learning (ML) for the specific end-to-end optimization of communication systems has caused a paradigm shift and enabled a fresh look at yielding RPN-resilience in coherent transmission. In 2017, O’Shea *et al* [2] introduced the concept of an autoencoder (AE) for the physical layer. A system, fully defined in software, that merges neural networks (NNs) and communication systems to learn constellations and demappers that maximize the throughput through an additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) channel. Since then, this concept has taken on, and evolved into end-to-end optimization of the several building blocks of the DSP stack. Hence, it is only logical that we try to somehow improve the resilience to laser phase noise in the system as well.

Several efforts have been made to fight the prevalence of residual phase noise in constellations. To date, most efforts into building resilience to the detrimental impacts of RPN have mostly focused on either optimizing the demapper [3], optimizing the transmitted constellation [4, 5], or creating RPN-robust coding schemes [6]. In this work, we take a novel approach: we attempt to tackle the problem of RPN in the system from the pulse shaper/matched filter standpoint. By applying machine learning to end-to-end system parameter learning, we show that RPN robustness can effectively be addressed by the pulse shaper and matched filter.

2. End-to-End Learning Framework

To perform end-to-end optimization of several DSP subsystems, we have developed a Python framework, using the Tensorflow package, which we make available in a public repository, in [7]. For the results presented in this manuscript, this framework is utilized, and, in Fig. 1, we depict the blocks used in this work to optimize the pulse shaper and matched filter. In the transmitter, a vector of random symbols with a cardinality of 64 is generated, and these symbols are then mapped into a uniform 64QAM constellation, and two real-valued vectors are output, for the I and Q components. Afterward, the signal is upsampled to 2 samples per symbol (SpS) and pulse shaped. Here, one of two filters can be considered: (i) either a 63-tap classical root-raised cosine (RRC) filter, with a roll-off of 0.1, for baseline, filtering independently the I and Q vectors; or (ii) a 63-tap 2×2 real-valued filter, which is initialized randomly and is to be optimized, outputting I and Q vectors that are a combination of the initial I and Q signals. Then, the signal enters the channel, which includes low-pass filtering, with a combination of a 4th order Gaussian filter, with a 3 dB bandwidth at half the sampling frequency, and a digital brick wall filter, which is initially set to have a cut-off frequency also at half the sampling frequency, unless stated otherwise. Then, we add residual phase noise to the system and AWGN. The residual phase noise is modeled as a complex exponential whose argument is a random Gaussian variable with zero mean and variance given by σ_{RPN}^2 , which is projected onto the I and Q signals. The AWGN noise is also added to I and Q signals, whose variance will be such that it meets a training signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). At the receiver, the signal is filtered with a 63-tap matched filter, which, similar to the pulse shaper, can have one of two configurations: (i) either a classical root-raised cosine (RRC) filter, with a roll-off of 0.1; or (ii) a 2×2 real-valued filter, which is initialized randomly and

Fig. 1. Diagram of the end-to-end tool [7] used for the optimization of the pulse shaper and matched filter. Only the blocks used in this implementation are shown.

is to be optimized, jointly with the transmitted pulse shape. The signal is then downsampled and demapped, with a classical minimum distance demapper, and the SNR and generalized mutual information (GMI) are computed. When optimizing the pulse shaper and the matched filter, this optimization is conducted via machine learning tools from the Tensorflow toolbox, and the filters' taps are optimized to maximize the GMI after demapping, with the Adam optimizer. This GMI end-to-end optimization technique is based on the one presented in [8].

3. Results

To underscore the impact of residual phase noise in classical 64QAM transmission, in Figs. 2a-c we plot the first quadrant of the 64QAM constellation when under the effect of RPN after using RRC as pulse shaper and matched filter for three values of σ_{RPN}^2 , 0.01, 0.03, and 0.05. In these figures, we have set the operating SNR to 40 dB, to isolate the impact of RPN. Conversely, if we allow our framework to optimize the system performance, converging to a learned pulse shape (LPS), we get Figs. 2d-f, for the same three values of σ_{RPN}^2 . It is remarkable how, indeed, allowing our learned pulse shape to have a 2×2 form, mixing information from the in-phase tributary of the constellation into the quadrature tributary, and vice versa, enabled resilience towards residual phase noise, and now the symbols are discernible again, even for large values of σ_{RPN}^2 . For a generalized study of the performance of our LPS vs. classical RRC, we show Fig. 2g, where we plot the received effective SNR vs. the AWGN SNR, for different levels of RPN, and both classical RRC and LPS. The AWGN SNR dictates how much random Gaussian noise is inserted into the system, whereas the effective SNR accounts for both AWGN and RPN, after matched filtering. We trained the LPS for each SNR and RPN value. When we do not insert any RPN in the system ($\sigma_{\text{RPN}}^2 = 0$), we see that both the RRC and the LPS curves follow a linear trend, as expected, and the effective SNR is equal to the AWGN SNR. However, when we add RPN to the system, this is no longer the case, we have an SNR penalty, given by the difference between AWGN SNR and effective SNR. We can see that, as we increase the amount of RPN, indeed the RRC produces a larger SNR penalty, while the LPS can minimize the penalty. For

Fig. 2. In (a), (b), and (c), we show the first quadrant of a 64QAM signal after matched filtering with RRC with σ_{RPN}^2 equal to 0.01, 0.03, and 0.05, respectively. In (d), (e), and (f), we show the same, but for our learned pulse shape (LPS). In (g), we assess the SNR performance of both RRC and LPS under different levels of RPN.

Fig. 3. In (a), the 63-taps of the 2×2 real-valued LPS are shown, for a working SNR of 18 dB, in the training case of $\sigma_{\text{RPN}}^2 = 0.05$. In (b), we plot the respective spectrum of the LPS-shaped signal at the output of the channel. The SNR penalty from having RPN in the system is shown in (c), and the respective GMI gain from LPS over RRC is shown in (d).

completeness, we show in Fig. 3a the $2 \times 2 \times 63$ taps of the LPS, for a training SNR of 18 dB and $\sigma_{\text{RPN}}^2 = 0.05$. We can see it differs from a standard filter. The matched filter, optimized independently, is not shown here because it converged to a similar, time-reversed filter, with the exception that the cross terms ($I \rightarrow Q$ and $Q \rightarrow I$) are swapped.

To shed light on the origin of this gain, and understand the trade-offs, Fig. 3b shows the obtained spectra at the output of the channel, for standard RRC, and for our LPS. The SNR is fixed at 18 dB and $\sigma_{\text{RPN}}^2 = 0.05$. From the analysis of this figure, we see how the gain of LPS comes from a broadening of the spectrum, although it still works at only two samples per symbol. In Fig. 3c, we assess the SNR penalty introduced by the increasing RPN in the effective SNR at an operating SNR of 18 dB. Since the observed spectral broadening is undesirable, we tried to restrict the normalized bandwidth (BW) of the brick wall filter in the channel model to see if the LPS could keep the RPN-resilience at a BW equal to that of RRC. The dashed black line in Fig. 3c shows the baseline penalty of the RRC pulse shape, which can be as high as 4 dB for $\sigma_{\text{RPN}}^2 = 0.05$. The unrestricted LPS, allowing the full bandwidth (BW=1), in turn, can keep this penalty low, at roughly 1 dB. If we restrict the normalized BW of the LPS to 0.6, all performance advantage is lost, and the penalty is equal to that of the RRC filter, showing that indeed the advantage comes from the excess bandwidth. In Fig. 3d, we show the GMI gain when going from RRC to the improved LPS. We observe that we can achieve quite interesting gains, as high as 1 bits/sym, and, if we limit the system BW to 80 %, we can still get a significant gain of 0.2 bits/sym.

4. Conclusions

In this work, we have introduced a novel learned pulse shape (LPS) capable of withstanding significant residual phase noise. This pulse shape is particularly suited for low baud rate transmission scenarios, where residual phase noise poses a significant challenge due to the difficulty of phase tracking over long symbol periods, and bandwidth constraints are less critical. The proposed LPS allows for the relaxation of the carrier phase estimation (CPE) subsystem, enabling the transmission of high-order modulation formats with reduced performance penalties.

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